

THE NAOS OF THE DECADES AND THE ASTRAL ASPECTS OF DIVINE JUDGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Naos of the Decades is a remarkable monument due to the originality of its decoration and the unusual history of its discovery. Its reconstruction is the result of a veritable puzzle of archaeological history: the roof of the chapel, which is exhibited in the Louvre ever since 1817, was discovered on land and has never been under water. Its base and rear were brought to light in 1940 during underwater excavations carried out by Prince ʿOmar Toussoun. And finally, several slabs of its lateral walls (major fragments of both side walls of the Naos) were discovered under water, in Abukir Bay, by the European Institute for Underwater Archæology (IEASM) in collaboration with the Department of Underwater Archæology of the Egyptian Supreme Council of Antiquities (SCA). One of these recently discovered slabs revealed a mythological text about the creation of the decanal stars, of which there exists no other known version! This contains an original Cosmogony which throws an entirely new light on the mythological functions which the Egyptians attributed to these stars ever since the most ancient time. The *Book of Nūt*, whose oldest currently known version dates back to the New Kingdom, explains in detail the course of the decanal stars and the Sun, but it was demonstrated that it goes back at the very least to the Middle Kingdom. Its data allow establishing a connection between the five figures engraved in each frame of the decades on the Naos and the various stages of the decanal stars during their annual and daily trajectories. Hence, we also present here a new astronomical and mythological interpretation of the Naos of the Decades in the light of the astronomical text of the *Book of Nūt*. On the Naos of the Decades, Rē^c issued a decree attributing the power of life and death to the decanal stars. It further specifies that the god Shū stands at their head. This outstanding monument displays frames containing five figures surrounded by legends. Each frame is attributed to one decade and contains an astrological text aiming at the destruction of the enemies of Egypt. The actions of these decanal stars depend on the hour of day or night, according to the Sun's position in the sky relative to them. Decisions on life and death are not accidental, but are determined by the «Books», i.e.: by the results of the divine judgements. The Naos itself appears to be one of them, a *Book of Shū* entrusted by this god to Sekhmet/Sirius, regent of the decans, to have these judgements carried out by the decans in her retinue.

I. INTRODUCTION

The decorative composition, the unusual iconography, and the variety and wealth of its texts, at the same time mythological, astronomical and medical, render the Naos of the Decades a particularly complex and original monument. The successive discovery of its fragments, spreading over more than two centuries, lead to an example of archaeological history¹, as well as a true puzzle of Egyptology². In addition and interestingly, each new discovery contradicted previous interpretations.

¹ See YOYOTTE, 1954: 79-81.

² See GODDIO, 2003: 168-69 and in this volume (pp. 181-87); VON BOMHARD, 2011: 107-12.

FIGURE 1: Louvre D37: the roof of the Naos of the Decades: a) front-right; and b) right-rear angles.

II. HISTORY OF THE DISCOVERY

II.1. THE ROOF: The uppermost part of the Naos, a non inscribed pyramid roof to which are attached the inscribed uppermost parts of the walls, was found in 1777 on land at Abukir, and was brought into the Louvre Museum in 1817 (Louvre D37). It greatly interested Champollion in the context of his studies of the division of time of the ancient Egyptians³, because the outer surfaces of the remaining walls displayed frames, each covering a ten-day period, a *decade* (δεκάς) [FIG. 1]. These frames were illustrated by a so far unattested sequence of three vertically disposed figures: a human-headed bird, a falcon-headed sphinx and a lion-headed ram *passant* [FIG. 2].

FIGURE 2: Louvre D37: two decade frames. [From *Description de l'Égypte*, Antiquités: V, pl. 48].

Brugsch⁴ wrote a brief but remarkable study of this object, called «The Louvre calendar» at the time. He suggested that the Naos must have been dedicated to the god Shū of Saft 'el-

³ See CHAMPOLLION, 1841: 73-136.

⁴ See BRUGSCH, 1968: 179-84.

Henna, since the town's ancient Egyptian name, Yat–Nebes, appears several times in the texts, and further that it must concern the decanal stars, because the year was divided into 36 Decades. Both propositions turned out to be true. Much later, Clère⁵ had the merit to identify the cartouche of Nectanebo I, first king of the 30th dynasty, on the much abraded front lintel. The disposition of the decade frames on the missing surfaces that he proposed was contradicted by the next discovery.

II.2. THE BASE AND REAR WALL: Two big fragments were found in 1940 by Prince 'Omar Toussoun⁶ during his underwater research in the Bay of Abukir. In the same year, the prince donated these items to the Helleno–Roman Museum of Alexandria (JE 25.774). Due to the very particular decoration of the outside rear wall, the Habachi⁷ brothers realized that the two parts discovered by Toussoun and the Louvre Calendar were part of the same Naos. Thus, they took up the study of the monument. The first surprise was that each decade frame contains, in fact, five figures one above the other, instead of three: a standing mummy with a canine head and a reclining mummy complete the series of the bird, the sphinx and the ram **[FIG. 3 & 8]**. These figures are surrounded by legends which are the same for all decades, excepting some variations of spelling and disposition. Each decade frame also contains a small «astrological» text in two or three columns that is different for each decade, but begins with the same opening words: «The great god, in the beginning [...]» and goes on describing this great god's actions, aiming at the destruction of rebels and foreign people. The Habachi brothers⁸ translated the legends of the five figures, but put off the study of these «astrological» notes, which were later translated by Leitz⁹.

FIGURE 3: The 29th, 30th and 31st Decade fields on the rear wall between two lines of *Horizontal Text*.
[Photograph by Ch. Gerigk, © Franck Goddio, IEASM].

⁵ See CLÈRE, 1950: 143-52.

⁶ See TOUSSOUN, 1934: 342-54.

⁷ See HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 251-63.

⁸ See *op. cit.*: 256-58.

⁹ See LEITZ, 1995: 13-38.

The second revelation provided by the new fragments is the image on the rear inside wall which shows the statue that the Naos contained: the god Shū of Saft 'el-Henna as a sitting lion. The third information concerns the setting of the decade frames in three superimposed registers separated by bands of larger hieroglyphs [FIG. 3]. These lines were to be read from the top to bottom, and continued on the missing sides of the Naos. They constitute what we term *Horizontal Text*, because almost all others on the Naos are set in columns. They deal with Yat–Nebes and the decanal stars¹⁰.

Regarding the supposed disposition of the decade frames on the missing lateral walls, Leitz followed the Habachi brothers. Once again, this turned out to be erroneous due to another major archæological occurrence.

II.3. THE LEFT AND THE RIGHT WALLS: In 1999, over two centuries after the roof was found on land, the Institut Européen d'Archéologie Sous-Marine found several huge fragments of the lateral walls¹¹ in the Bay of Abukir. The left side¹² provided another surprise: instead of containing decade frames like the other sides, the upper part of this wall reveals a text in columns which precedes the 1st Decade frame. Even more extraordinary, this text is a Cosmogony so far unknown which describes the creation of the decanal stars and the functions they are to carry out. In addition, the new fragments permit us to definitely establish the order of the decade frames [FIG. 4].

FIGURE 4: The four sides of the Naos showing the various fragments, their origins and the positioning of the 37 Decade frames. [Diagram: L. von Bomhard, IEASM].

¹⁰ See HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 254; LEITZ, 1995: 6-7; VON BOMHARD, 2008: 196.

¹¹ See *supra* and cf. GODDIO, 2003: 169; GODDIO, 2006: 57; GODDIO, 2007: 43-44; GODDIO, 2008: 41.

¹² The terms for «left» and «right» were defined by Clère (cf. CLÈRE, 1950: 145) and the Habachi brothers (cf. HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 255), that is as seen by an observer facing the monument.

III. THE RECITAL OF THE CREATION OF THE UNIVERSE

The text in columns on the left wall, which precedes the frame of the 1st Decade, is divided into two parts of equal length, both dealing with the decanal stars¹³. The first part describes the creative act of the god Shū uplifting the sky, placing himself as the atmosphere between his daughter Nūt (the Sky) and his son Geb (the Earth). Once the sky and the air are created, the god sets up «the disks»¹⁴ and the decanal stars in the firmament. Then, the celestial bodies can begin their cycles, and their passing through the sky marks the beginning of time¹⁵ which is counted by the cycle of the stars: day and night according to the Sun; the decades at the rhythm of the decanal stars. With the initiation of time, the creator also installs death and sickness among all creatures. Although the beginning of the text is lost, the recital indicates that the decanal stars are created by Shū from the «souls of the gods» (~ *b3w nḥw*).

FIGURE 5: The front view of the Naos.
[Photograph: Ch. Gerigk, © Franck Goddio IEASM].

The second part of the recital declaims Rē^c's words dictating a decree to Thoth: a temple is to be built at Yat–Nebes for «the souls of the gods», i.e.: the decans, whose mission is to decide on life and death throughout the Universe. Rē^c ordered that the temple should be located on a straight line of sight from the mound of the Jujube Tree (*I3t-Nbs*) which is connected to the *Headdress House* (*Pr-Brt*). The 36 stars are called the *Guides of Rē^c*, the *Children of Rē^c*, and the *Children of Sekhmet, Nekhbet, Bastet and Wadjyt*. Above all, they are *Thoth's emissaries*. Rē^c then

¹³ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 54-55.

¹⁴ The term «disk» indicates the Sun and the Moon, but also the Planets.

¹⁵ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 59; VON BOMHARD, 2011: 114.

decreed that the god Shū should stand at the head of the decans.

IV. THE GOD SHŪ OF THE NAOS

The rear inside wall of the chapel shows a real size image (four palms) of the statue that the Naos contained: the god Shū as a sitting lion covered by two high feathers and a uræus [FIG. 5]. The texts next to it indicate that it was made of silver overlaid with fine gold. Yoyotte¹⁶ noted the connection to a drawing by Sharpe of a block framed in a wall in an Alexandrian house, now lost. It displays the goddess Tefnūt, in the same position and of exactly the same dimensions, with similar captions¹⁷. Yoyotte shrewdly concluded that the two monuments must have been twins. The aspect of Shū as a sitting lion, shown in the Naos of the Decades, is apparently not documented before¹⁸.

FIGURE 6: Left upper wall: part of a panel above the Cosmogony.
[Drawing: A. L'Amoulen].

IV.1. SHŪ, BEARER OF THE STARS: Shū «at the head of the decans» is seemingly not attested in any other text than the Cosmogony of the Naos of the Decades. Still, the notion that the god of the air and the winds moves the stars is a very ancient one, since it appears as early as the *Pyramid Texts*¹⁹ where the deceased, assimilated with the Sun, is carried by the winds; in the *Coffin Texts*²⁰, he moves together with them. The *Book of Nūt*²¹ explains that the visible stars, i.e.: the Sun during the day and the stars in the night, follow their course outside Nūt's body, which implies that they wander through the air; in the temples of Ptolemaic times²², the winds move the Sun, the Moon, and the decanal stars²³. It therefore appeared perfectly logical to the Egyptian mind that the god of air and wind should control the decans. This function of Shū clearly justifies his connection with the decade frames decorating the outer façade of the monument. This very function also explains the god's «astrological» role, since it is he who is responsible for the respective positions of the stars in the sky, depending on the moment of the day, and also on the decade of the year. And it is exactly for this evident reason that we

¹⁶ See YOYOTTE, 1954: 81-82.

¹⁷ See SHARPE, 1837: pl. 20.

¹⁸ This iconography should be added to LGG 7, 34c-d.

¹⁹ Cf. *PT*: §§ 324-326; MARAVELIA, 2006: 95.

²⁰ Cf. *CT*, I: 266c-266e; II: 29a-30a and 37g; MARAVELIA, 2006: 142, 144-45.

²¹ See NEUGEBAUER & PARKER, 1960: 67, 71; VON LIEVEN, 2007: 80, 85-86.

²² See SAUNERON, 1963: 208-09, 239; DU BOURGUET, 2002: 106.

²³ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 39-43; VON BOMHARD, 2010: 166; VON BOMHARD, 2011: 115-116. [EDITOR'S NOTE: A comparison could be attempted to the fact that all celestial bodies were conceived as sky-divinities inside celestial boats (*wšw*) and with the related micrographic sails that the deceased bears in order to symbolize the existence of air/wind (~ *šw n ḥh*) in the hereafter in various tomb- and *BD*-paintings].

have identified «the great god» in the astrological notes as Shū himself —god of the air, of the atmosphere, of the æther and of the light—, that is the tutelary god/divinity of the Naos of the Decades²⁴.

IV.2. SHŪ OF THE NEBES–TREE — A THOTH–SHŪ: An anthropomorphous and ibidocephalous Thoth is shown twice on the Naos, sitting and writing on a tablet; the first time in the upper part of the left side wall [FIG. 6], and once again in the lower part of the right wall [FIG. 7].

1. On the upper left wall, above the Cosmogony, it can be seen in a partly destroyed image as the first of three still visible sitting divinities, only the feet of the third one are still preserved [FIG. 6]. In front of Thoth, there are three columns of retrograde writing, with the uppermost part missing. They describe the god as *Lord of the Books* and relate him to the *h3tyw*-genies in a sentence of the type: «the *h3tyw*-genies act [according to his commands] in Yat–Nebes». Under the sitting gods, the end of a sentence, which seems to stand as a caption for the entire image, says: «[...] in Yat–Nebes, *she* stands on the sand to the south of the Headdress House». This legend could concern a temple (feminine in Egyptian) containing the sitting gods. The term «sand to the south» appears again on the base of the left wall of the Naos, in the context of the temple of the *šm3yw*-genies. The second representation of Thoth on the right wall sets him in relation to that temple.

FIGURE 7: The base of the right wall.
[Drawing: A. L'Amoulen].

2. On the base of the right wall, Thoth is shown in the same attitude as above, except for the hemhem-crown [FIG. 7]. Five knife-bearing genies in front of him seem to wait for his orders. A text in unfortunately damaged columns in front of these figures begins with: «As regards the temple of the *šm3yw* [...]». It goes on to describe the actions of the *šm3yw*-genies, which were given the power of life and death that Rē^c granted to the decans in the recital of the creation. The «great temple of Thoth at the head of the *šm3yw* at Yat–Nebes» is also mentioned. This Thoth of Yat–Nebes «at the head of the *šm3yw*» should be linked to Shū «at the head of the 36 stars» of the Cosmogony. As at Pnoubis, this Thoth of the Nebes is a hypostasis of Shū²⁵. The Thoth of Pnoubis, incidentally, is termed «Shū, son of Rē^c»²⁶. At Philæ, he is the «Thoth of

²⁴ C. Leitz (see LEITZ, 1995: 4; LEITZ, 2010: 184) sees the great god as the decan of the decade concerned. Additionally, J.–F. Quack (see QUACK, 2010: 175) does not comment on the identity of the great god, and does not mention the god Shū in his study of the monument.

²⁵ See SAUNERON & YOYOTTE, 1952: 163–66.

²⁶ See INCONNU–BOCQUILLON, 1988: 52–53; INCONNU–BOCQUILLON, 2001: 138–42.

Pnoub, Lord of Truth, Master of Judgement, He who resides in the House of the Books»²⁷.

The books in question are the *Books of Calamities of He who Destroys Lifetime*, containing the census (*hsb*) and the lists of those who must be punished or destroyed²⁸. The Thoth of the Naos is called «Lord of the Books» in the display which precedes the recital of the creation [FIG. 6]. He commands the decans in the Cosmogony, the *h3tyw*-genies in the panel above the Cosmogony [FIG. 6], and he stands at the head of the *sm3yw*-genies in the base of the right wall [FIG. 7]. He is a kind of Thoth–Shū connected with Divine Judgement, like the one at Pnoub. The two aspects of Shū, «Bearer of the Stars» and «Lord of Judgement», appear again in the decade frames. All the above notions allow understanding the interpretation of the five figures, and even of the entire monument.

V. THE FIVE FIGURES OF THE DECADE FRAMES

The decade frames engraved on the outer surfaces of the Naos represent a decoration that is unique up to now. There are 37 frames, one for each decade of the Egyptian year, the 37th accounting for the five epagomenal days. All are set up in the same way [FIG. 8] and the legends surrounding the five figures are the same in each decade; only the «astrological» text written in the columns alongside the last four figures varies.

V.1. THE FIGURES AND THEIR LEGENDS: In this Section we are going to examine with some detail the various figures and their legends or «captions».

1. The vignette with the bird is bigger than the four that follow it, and is set above them like a title frame. A human-headed bird bearing an encircled star [EDITOR'S NOTE: possibly alluding to the notion of *Hadēs/Dw3t*, where the decans are resting and wherefrom they re-appear as this specific-one] stands in a barque set on a snake. The bird is preceded by the sign of the flame. Favourable climatic conditions «in his decade» are requested from it.

2. In the second image, a hawk-headed sphinx sits on a pedestal in the form of a porch (*sbht*) in which the name of Yat–Nebes is inscribed. She holds a bow and arrows and is qualified as the «Lord of Combat». She is sent on earth during her decade to bring death²⁹ to the *tmyw*³⁰.

3. In the third image, a ram *passant* with the head of a lion and bearing the southern crown, is said to be «the Lord of the Length of Life». Demands of life are addressed to him during his decade.

4. Next down, a standing mummy with a canine head, bearing the northern crown, is said to be «his image in his temple, inside the House of Soped (*Pr-Spd*) at Yat–Nebes». Offerings are made during its decade.

5. In the last vignette, a human mummy reclining on a funerary bier is said to be «his living *b3* forever», and the caption says «letting his body rest in the necropolis». The name of this necropolis, inscribed underneath the couch, is the «Headdress House». Requests for a beautiful burial are addressed to this divinity.

²⁷ See JUNKER, 1917: 10. On Judgement after death in general, cf. also ZANDEE, 1960: 25-31.

²⁸ See HERBIN, 2004: 185.

²⁹ Throughout the monument, the word *death* is spelt *mr*.

³⁰ The word, spelt with two knives, is translated as *evildoers* (cf. HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 257, n. 16).

V.2. THE ASTRAL INTERPRETATION: From the very beginning of the study of the Louvre fragment, it was obvious that the figures concerned the decanal stars, because each field with the five figures was attributed to a ten-day period. Brugsch³¹ was the first to realize that the engravings were related to both the decanal stars and to the god Shū. The Habachi brothers³² had already suggested that the five figures were different aspects of the decans.

Text around the bird:

"The demands for water, winds and crops depend on him in his decade in 'Bt-nbs'".

Text around the sphinx:

"It is in this guise of the Lord of Combat that he stands up ('h') and comes forth from Hwt-nbs in his decade of his envoy on earth. It is he who causes death among the evildoers".

Text around the ram:

"The Lord of Life. His ba living on earth is in this form of Master of lifetime. The demands of life depend on him in his decade in 'Bt-nbs'".

Text around the standing mummy:

"This is his image ('hm) in his temple in the domain of Spd in 'Bt-nbs'. May offerings be presented according (r) to each temple in his decade".

Text around the reclining mummy:

"Letting his body rest in the necropolis. His ba living forever. The requests for a good burial depend on him in his decade in 'Bt-nbs'".

Text facing the bird: Identification of the decade of the year; presenting offerings:

"1st month of 3It, days 11-20. To present offerings by the king to this god in 'Bt-nbs, in the year of terror, to protect the country from impurity".

Text facing the remaining four figures: Astrological, mythical or climatic comments (different for each decade):

[1] The Great God at the Beginning: it is he who brings death to the land of... (?) He who is subjected to his morbidic air had the aspect of a man [...].

[2] His face is red, sweat pearls on his front like scent... He will be as one destroyed by a [fever]...

[3] of one day. He (the Great God) throws him on the ground: he will not live, in accordance (?) (r) with his (the Great God's) massacre among the chiefs of all the foreign lands. It will happen that hands will be tied (?)".

FIGURE 8: The five images and their texts in the frame of the 2nd Decade.

THE THEORY OF LEITZ: Leitz³³ then had the ingenious idea to link the first figure, the human-headed bird, and the two last-ones, the standing and the reclining mummy, to the contents of the *Book of Nūt*, which mentions human-headed birds, and which compares the decanal cycle to the course of human life. The decanal stars are said to have «their funerals like those of humans». Their 70 days of absence from the sky are linked to the length of the mummification process³⁴. Consequently, Leitz suggested that the bird represented the period of the rise and ascension in the eastern sky³⁵ of the decan that inaugurates the decade; the sphinx that of its culmination³⁶; the ram and the standing mummy that of its decline in the western sky³⁷; and

³¹ See BRUGSCH, 1968: 179-84.

³² See HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 262-63.

³³ See LEITZ, 1995: 8-13.

³⁴ See NEUGEBAUER & PARKER, 1960: 73-74; VON LIEVEN, 2007: 87-89.

³⁵ A period of 80 days of duration, according to the *Book of Nūt*.

³⁶ A decan culminates during 120 days: first, it indicates the 12th hour of the night from the 81st to the 90th day after its heliacal rise, then the 11th night hour in the following decade, then the 10th and so forth ... until the 1st night hour from the 191st to the 200th day after its rise.

³⁷ Lasting 90 days.

the reclining mummy the period of invisibility³⁸. Leitz believes that the decan was astrologically active only during its first culmination (81st to 90th day). The astrological text inscribed in a decade would therefore not concern the Decade **D** where it is inscribed, but the Decade **D+8**. With this theory, Leitz aims at explaining why the Nile flood is mentioned in the astrological text of the 28th Decade, and would come to happen 8 decades later, i.e.: during the 36th, at the very beginning of the year³⁹. This setup could fit the date of inundation. However, it cannot fit the astronomical text of the 37th «Decade» for the epagomenal days, mentioning calamities and the yearly plague habitually attached to those days, and which would occur during the 8th Decade according to the theory of Leitz. Above all, it is particularly disturbing that a text inscribed in one decade should be attributed to quite another one. Moreover, each of the five images contains the words «during his decade», which obviously means the one indicated in front of the bird. According to Leitz the figures would cover several decades: the bird 8, the sphinx 12, the ram together with the standing mummy 9, and the reclining mummy 7 (in total 36). Only the bird would at least partly correspond to the decade indicated in front of it.

FIGURE 9: The proposed theory. The various aspects of Shū/Sun during 24 hours.
[Diagram: L. von Bomhard, IEASM].

THE PROPOSED THEORY: Leitz's excellent idea to link the five figures to the decanal cycle as described in the *Book of Nūt* must certainly be maintained, on the condition of considering not just the annual cycle of a single decanal star, but the disposition of all of them, as they are visible during any given decade. This is expressed in the *Book of Nūt's* passage: «[...] 8 stars are in the eastern sky, 12 work⁴⁰ in the centre of the sky; they are 36 in total [...] there are 9 stars in the West [...] 29 are in the sky and 7 are in the *Dw3t*»⁴¹. In the proposed theory the bird would represent the decan rising during the indicated decade; the sphinx would be linked to the 8 ascending stars, the ram to the 12 culminating, the standing mummy to the 9 declining, and the reclining mummy to the 7 invisible stars during that decade. However, the Sun

³⁸ Lasting 70 days.

³⁹ For another explanation of this date of the flood, see VON BOMHARD, 2008: 99-101; VON BOMHARD, 2011: 120, n. 95. The year described on the Naos of the Decades would be the one of the creation of the decanal system (as well as, for the same reason, the one in list U in the *Book of Nūt*).

⁴⁰ The *work* (*b3k*) means the task of culmination of these stars.

⁴¹ See NEUGEBAUER & PARKER, 1960: 58-60; VON LIEVEN, 2007: 69-71.

must also be considered, and the four last figures would — in fact — represent Shū/Sun when it crosses the sky during the days (and the nights) of the decade. Its course is marked by the visible decans (and the invisible—ones during the night) of the current decade [FIG. 9]. The course of the Sun is set in a decanal frame that varies with each decade. The Sun rises in the morning in the part of the sky where the 8 ascending decans are located. At noon, it is with the decan that culminates at that hour, according to the decade. In the evening, the Sun descends into the West in the part of the sky where the declining decans shine, and disappears below the western horizon, joining the 7 decans in the *Dw3t*. The presence of the Sun in certain decans is supposed to provoke «astrological effects», same as it is assumed to do in later times, passing through the signs of the Zodiac. In this way, the Naos of the Decades seems to stand at the beginnings of astrology⁴². On the Naos of the Decades, the effects are mythological rather than astrological.

V.3. MYTHOLOGICAL INTERPRETATIONS: In this Section we are going to discuss and comment on the related mythological interpretations.

1. The Human-Headed Bird is a hieroglyph that reads *b3(i)* for «soul», and the recital of the creation on the Naos says — like other texts⁴³ — that the decanal stars are the souls of the gods. The star on the bird's head which is usually found on the heads of the hour goddesses, fits in with the hourly function of the decans. The barque is often the means of movement of celestial bodies, like Sirius and Orion. The serpent evokes the *Book of the Heavenly Cow*: «the *b3w* of all the gods and all the goddesses are in the serpents»⁴⁴. The flame in front of the bird, which faces the word «impurity» on all decade frames, illustrates evil repulsed by the fire/uræus of the star. And lastly, it seems natural that requests for good climatic conditions be addressed to it, because the rise of the stars is linked to the seasons⁴⁵. Traunecker had noted the abundance of meteorological indications on the Naos⁴⁶. The bird, as the image of the decan that inaugurates the decade indicated in front of it, represents only this star (not the Sun!), and the vignette that contains is a kind of title that controls the four following figures. These are linked to the successive points of the compass where the Sun is observed during the day: East, South, West, and during its disappearance in the night.

2. The Hieracocephalous Sphinx, as the Habachi brothers had already noted⁴⁷, greatly resembles the god Sopdu-Shū son of Rē^c on the grand Naos of Cairo⁴⁸, where it is called «Sopdu Lord of the East who vanquishes the Asiatics»⁴⁹. We know that Sopdu is in charge of defending Egypt in the East. This god is a form of Shū, and its temple is at Saft `el-Henna, Yat-Nebes, in the East of Egypt. In the *Horizontal Text* that separates the registers of decades, this town is said to be the *sbht* of the sky, from where the Sun seems to come forth, which explains the sphinx's *sbht* pedestal. The Lord of Combat thus assumes a «warrior's» role in defending the country, because we know that Saft `el-Henna at the opening of Wadi Tumulāt, a possible invasion route for Asiatics, was a fortified town. The Lord of Combat also has a mythological function: the god is a Shū/Sopdu/Sun who destroys the evildoers at the *sbht* of the horizon,

⁴² On astrology in ancient Egypt, see CUMONT, 1937. *Contra* astrology and its fallacy, see MARAVELIA, 2010: 83-87.

⁴³ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 56, n. b; 63-65.

⁴⁴ See HORNUNG, 1982: 47; GUILHOU, 1989: 13; cf. also GUILHOU, 1984: 90.

⁴⁵ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 86; VON BOMHARD, 2012: 88.

⁴⁶ See TRAUNECKER, 1990: 23.

⁴⁷ See HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 261-62.

⁴⁸ See NAVILLE, 1887: pl. 2, register 6; pl. 5, register 2.

⁴⁹ See *op. cit.*: pl. 1, registers 1-3; pl. 2, register 6; pl. 4, register 6.

i.e.: upon his rising in the morning.

3. The Lion-Headed Ram. As the two previous images evoke the stars in their ascending, and the two last-ones in their declining phase, the ram seems to stand at the cross-roads between those two periods, i.e.: the time of culmination. The southern crown seems to confirm this, because for the Northern Hemisphere, where Egypt is situated, the culminating Sun and the decanal stars indicate the South. The lion's head reminds us also that this animal represents the noon Sun in the cryptogram *srpt.m3i.sr*⁵⁰. The «Lord of Life» is an epithet that fits well the Sun at its height. The ram with wavy horizontal horns (*ovis longipes palæoægyptiacus*) is also a hieroglyph standing for the word «b3», and the legend «his living b3 on earth» fits both the b3 of Rē^c and the b3 of Shū, which the *Coffin Texts* [IV: 178f-g] show as equivalent: «I am the b3 of Shū who has become Rē^c [...] and vice versa». The ram would thus be the noon Sun, situated next to the decan supposed to culminate at midday.

4. The Standing Mummy. The canine head evokes Anubis or Wepwawet who guide the steps of the deceased on the paths of the Occident (*Imntt*). The northern crown points in that direction since, in the *Book of Nūt*, the entrance to the *Dw3t* is situated in the northwest⁵¹. Above all, the figure recalls the god Tekem or Rekem⁵², very probably one of the various forms of the *Opener of Ways* (*Wp-w3wt*), since his role is to open the path in the western horizon⁵³. This god is connected with the judges of the Divine Court to which the deceased addresses himself in the following manner: «Hail to you, perfect *k3w*, lords of the goods [...] may you be clement to me and render justice to the mouth through which I speak! [...] I know the name of the god on whose nose you place the food: Tekem is his name. He opens the western horizon, and he knows the eastern horizon [...]». We understand that if the deceased is «justified», he has access to the food that allows his *k3* to survive. This food granted by the Judges of the Divine Court of Justice must be set down «in front of the nose» of Tekem. Now, offerings are indeed mentioned facing the standing mummy, and on all decans the legends are disposed in such a way, so as to place the word *offerings* (*htpw*) precisely opposite the pointed nose of the mummy [FIG. 8]. According to the texts that accompany it, the standing mummy is «his image in his temple, in the House of Soped». This leads to the conclusion that this god, too, is a variation/hypostasis of Shū/Sopdu, since he is honoured in the «House of Soped». The standing mummy with the head of a jackal would thus be a form of the declining Sun.

5. The Reclining Mummy. The image and the texts that surround it refer to the state of death: invisibility for the stars and disappearance for the individual. For the Sun, it is its nightly disappearance, during which it is said to travel in the company of the seven invisible decanal stars. The words «his b3 living forever» recall «his b3 living on earth», which is the legend for the ram standing for the culminating Sun. The reclining mummy evokes the regeneration and the next reappearance of the Sun. The name of the necropolis where it regenerates is «the Headdress House» which alludes to the radiance of the Sun and to the point where it rises⁵⁴. The requests for a «beautiful burial» recall the beneficent action of one of the memphite *k3w* studied by Meeks⁵⁵, the divinities who determine destiny.

⁵⁰ See RYHINER, 1977: 126.

⁵¹ See NEUGEBAUER & PARKER, 1960: 66-67; VON LIEVEN, 2007: 77-78.

⁵² See LANZONE, 1974: 1262.

⁵³ Cf. *CT*, v: 197-98; *BD*: 72, 99.

⁵⁴ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 70-74.

⁵⁵ See MEEKS, 1963: 35-47.

V.4. THE FIVE FIGURES, DESTINY AND DIVINE JUDGEMENT: The «request for life» addressed to the ram and those for «a beautiful burial» to the reclining mummy are good deeds granted by two of the «*k3w* of Ptah», who are attested for the first time in the temple of Sety I at Abydos, in the New Kingdom, but are probably older. There are four of them, named *Šw*, *Ndm-ꜥnh*, *Iḥ-rmw*, and *Htp-i(3)d*. The first one presides over birth, the second grants a long and agreeable life, same as the third; the last one provides a «beautiful burial», which means a tomb and funerary offerings which allow survival of the deceased's *k3*. Shū, the first *k3* of Ptah, gives life to humans, same as he does to the stars, according to the recital of the creation on the Naos. The *k3* of Ptah named Shū is clearly one of the aspects of the god of the Naos of the Decades, the bearer of the stars linked to Divine Judgement. The decree of Rē^c, stipulating that Shū commands the decanal stars, which have the power of life and death, implicitly confers to Shū the role of the righter of wrongs: as the Lord of Combat, Shū gives death, as the Lord of Life, he provides a long life; in the form of Tekem, he grants provisions guaranteeing the survival of the *k3* of the *justified* (*m3ꜥ-hrw*); in the form of the reclining mummy, he confers eternity by regenerating him in the necropolis, as the Sun does in the «Headdress House».

The study of the Naos of the Decades permits to bring forth the «astral» aspect of the four Memphite *k3w*, since the individual destiny is linked on the monument to the position of the Sun and the decanal stars in the sky. It must be noted, too, that in the temples of Opet and Kom Ombo, these four *k3w* are mentioned on the upper parts, i.e.: the surfaces that are mostly dedicated to celestial objects. In addition, at Kom Ombo, they are related to the movements of the *b3iw* of the gods⁵⁶, illustrating the link between the four Memphite *k3w* and the decanal stars⁵⁷. At Dendera, the four *k3w* are set on the east and west walls of the *Pure Place* (*Wꜥbt*): this is the name of the place where Osiris and the deceased were embalmed and where the fate of the deceased was to be decided⁵⁸. The *Wꜥbt* is also indicated as the *gateway of the horizon* (*sbht-3ht*), a point of passage from earth to the hereafter, and the point where the Sun appears.

The correlation between the sunrise and the Divine Judgement is apparent as early as the *Coffin Texts* and the *Book of the Dead*. The site of execution in the East, at the gate of the horizon where the Sun appears, is mentioned in the *Coffin Texts* [CT, VI: 144] and in Chapters 93 and 176 of the *Book of the Dead*: the deceased who has not been justified does not — contrary to the Sun — reappear in the East. This is the «second death», definite this time, since neither his *k3* nor his *b3* survive⁵⁹. This notion is illustrated on the Naos of the Decades by the image of the sphinx, Lord of Combat, the rising Sun, perched on the gateway *sbht*, bringing a deserved death to the evildoers.

The three following figures are beneficial and concern only the justified. The lion-headed ram, Lord of Life, gives a long and agreeable life, as does the *k3*-spirit *Ndm-ꜥnh*. Although they illustrate a decline, the standing and the reclining mummy do not bring death; quite to the contrary, they are beneficial and grant survival after disappearance: the standing mummy, in the form of the setting Tekem-Shū-Sun, provides the offerings to the justified which grant survival of his *k3*, and gives him the capacity to pass the western and eastern horizons, like the Sun and the decans. The reclining mummy offers «a beautiful burial» to the just, which should be

⁵⁶ See GUTBUB, 1973: 385-94 ; VON BOMHARD, 2008: 63.

⁵⁷ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 63.

⁵⁸ See YOYOTTE, 1980-81: 99-101; VON BOMHARD, 2008: 199.

⁵⁹ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 187-89, 205. [EDITOR'S NOTE: Consequently, his *3h* (= *b3* + *k3*) can never be formed].

understood as the contrary of destruction, meaning that this divinity assures eternity and allows renaissance and regeneration.

In this way, the five figures tie together the destiny of the individual and the positions of the celestial bodies according to the hours. In the morning, the ascending Sun and decans exterminate the evil-ones in the porch of the horizon; when they culminate at noon, they give life to the just; in their decline during the evening, they give provisions to the *k3* of the deceased, and the invisible stars guarantee his everlastingness. This relation between the position of the Sun in the decans on the one hand, and the destiny of the individual on the other leads to the supposition that the Naos of the Decades appears as a forerunner of Egyptian astrology. The word *ῥοσκόπιον/horoscope* in its original sense of «observation of the hours» perfectly fits into the texts of the Naos, since the position of the decans depends on the hours. It must be noted, however, that at the time of the Naos, astrology had not yet been separated from religious Astronomy: the monument displays no outright prediction; the punishment of the enemies is a certainty and not a mere possibility, as is the recompensation of the justified-ones. Furthermore, sickness and death do not hit accidentally but only those who can harm Egypt, or who perturb the balance of the Cosmos by their behaviour (*M3ʿt ≠ isfi*)⁶⁰. This notion clearly results from analysis of the five figures, but also from the astrological texts attached to them.

VI. THE ASTROLOGICAL TEXTS

A short text set in two or three columns accompanies each decade. It always begins with the formula «The Great God at the Beginning [...]», and then usually continues with «[...] it is he who brings death to such and such a population or group of rebels». The great god does not hit individuals but entire groups or inimical populations. As god of the air, Shū acts through the winds, i.e.: the *breezes (dhrwt)* that transmit affliction. The evil that hits the entire group is described through the sickness symptoms of one individual. The god also initiates meteorological catastrophes, plant pollutions, or epidemics among cattle. All these actions on animals and plants are aimed at reducing hostile populations through famine and sickness. The names of such foreign people, classical enemies of Egypt «of the nine arcs», are given, but also the Persians (Decade 3), highly feared at the time of Nectanebo I.

These writings are actually veritable texts of execration aiming at the destruction of enemies through performative magic of associating sickness or massacre with the names of those that must perish. The Naos of the Decades must therefore be considered as a true war machine in pharaoh's service! For the period, it virtually corresponds to the modern notion of a nuclear strike force, since the Naos does indeed mobilize all the forces of the Cosmos in the defence of Egypt: Shū, god of the atmosphere, sends lethal winds, it is he who carries the Sun and the stars whose function is to strike down enemies, rebels, and all those susceptible to harm the orderly progress of the Cosmos. In order to fulfil this task, Shū commands the decanal stars using their power on life and death.

VII. THE BOOK OF SHŪ

On the monument, the god Shū is qualified as «Lord of Books», meaning that he holds in his hands census lists (*hsbw*) containing the names of those that must be eliminated. In the Ritual

⁶⁰ See MARAVELIA, 2007: 1248.

of *shṭp Shmt* it is said that Shū brings his Books to Sekhmet⁶¹. In that same ritual, this goddess is assimilated several times to Sirius, regent of the decans. We understand that the god of the atmosphere uses the troops of Sirius, «messengers of Thoth», to carry out his judgements. At the change of the annual cycle, Sirius, followed by his retinue of decans, is ready to implement the sentences of the Divine Judgement collected in the *Books of Shū* and to execute the troublemakers and the evildoers.

FIGURE 10: The *Book of Shū/Royal k3*.
[Diagram: L. von Bomhard, IEASM].

One may wonder if the Naos of the Decades is not itself a copy of one of these books, a kind of *Book of Shū*⁶², i.e.: a compilation of the names engraved and thus preserved in stone, for the eternal destruction of the enemies of Egypt.

We know that Shū is «the living royal *k3* of Rē», a notion probably of Memphite origin⁶³, and that the royal *k3* is assimilated to Shū⁶⁴ or, more precisely, to the air which is the *b3* of Shū⁶⁵.

⁶¹ See GOYON, 2006: 28; 30, n. 8.

⁶² See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 49, 188; VON BOMHARD, 2011: 135.

⁶³ See GUTBUB, 1973: 189.

⁶⁴ See *op. cit.*: 289, n. d; 439-41, n. d.

⁶⁵ See *op. cit.*: 100, 204-05.

This allows supposing that the cosmo–theocratic power of the royal *k3* is expressed through the powers of Shū, god of the atmosphere⁶⁶. Once Nectanebo I has become king, he is himself invested with the powers of Shū son of Rē^c [FIG. 10], in order to rule Egypt and apply justice.

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⁶⁶ See VON BOMHARD, 2008: 229-32, fig 109; VON BOMHARD, 2011: 135-36.

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